

Polarized intensity (mJy beam⁻¹)

0.22

0.23

0.24

0.25

Dec (J2000)

10 $z_{\text{Sp}}=1.9482$

56°14'20"

00"

13'40"

20"

100 kpc

16^h08^m24^s

22^s

20^s

18^s

RA (J2000)